

Moderator's Handbook

This Moderator's Handbook was created as part of the PARATUS project, which received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2021 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101073954.

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How to use the handbook

We prepared the Moderator's Handbook to provide an overview of the High Water Pantano online social simulation. The simulation was created for educators, researchers, and non-governmental organizations who wish to make their workshops more attractive and interactive. However, other parties interested in engaging pedagogical and capacity-building methods are also welcome to use the High Water Pantano simulation.

In the following sections of the handbook, you will find that some of them have the tag "Print it". This means you are encouraged to print them and utilize them in your workshop(s).

Short Introduction to Serious GamesPantano

Participatory learning processes in disaster risk preparedness often prove challenging. An innovative approach to actively engaging activities lies in serious games, especially those with social interactions. Serious games combine game elements and mechanics with a concrete goal, such as acquiring knowledge or increasing skills.

A serious game with social interactions involves a group exploring a complex reality. It places participants in situations where collaboration is a valid and beneficial option, while encouraging them to stand their ground. There is great untapped potential in serious games within the field of disaster risk preparedness. The methodology is suitable for conveying complex issues and for experiencing how politics and interactions work within societies. Experience-based learning combined with role-playing and gaming elements makes newly gained knowledge more lasting and impactful.

In a nutshell:

- ✓ The **shift in perspective**, inherent to all simulation games, **helps participants gain distance from their own views** and **foster empathy for different opinions**.
- ✓ A **risk-free environment encourages creative thinking** and reflecting on one's approach to problem-solving.
- ✓ This makes the method particularly **valuable for intercultural and inter-sectoral learning environments**.

Moderator's Role in the Workshop Process

Social simulation, like many other experiential exercises, requires a moderator. There are three main reasons for that.

1. This kind of engagement may be completely new to some participants, so a **moderator is needed to explain the rules and guide the simulation process.**
2. As simulations emulate challenging scenarios, participants can experience strong emotions. **The moderator's role is to create a supportive environment and ensure that everyone feels comfortable and safe throughout the workshop.**
3. The moderator guides the debriefing session, where **participants are encouraged to air out their emotions, analyze and reflect on their moves, and extract meaningful lessons from the shared experience.**

Debriefing

A "debriefing" ("reflection session") is a key element of any serious game-based workshop. A well-conducted debriefing helps **clarify events** that occurred during the simulation and **translate in-game experiences into real-world insights.**

Moderation tips and instructions for the High Water Pantano simulation are included in this Handbook. This means **prior experience as a facilitator is not required.** Establishing trust between the group and the moderator is crucial and may outweigh the facilitation expertise.

Workshop

The High Water Pantano simulation is set in a stylized world of a city called Pantano and a village called Phusicos. It is playable in either online or face-to-face settings.

In High Water Pantano participants take on the roles of policymakers, scientists, practitioners, or citizens. They experience a flood scenario from the perspective of one of these stakeholders and have the opportunity to make decisions regarding risk responses in the Phusicos region. Participants are challenged with several key questions: Does it have to end in tragedy? How resilient is Pantano? What are the costs of saving it? These are just some of the dilemmas they must confront.

The game emphasizes negotiations between diverse groups and individuals, each representing different perspectives, as they attempt to ensure safety and timely responses to the unfolding flood in the Phusicos region.

Target group

The High Water Pantano simulation is designed for a broad spectrum of stakeholders exposed to disaster-related risks. Its primary goal is to enhance disaster preparedness and resilience by offering a realistic and immersive experience. We invite participation from all sectors involved in disaster risk reduction, including students, citizens, first and second responders, community leaders, and local authorities.

This game offers a valuable opportunity to delve into the complexities of managing systemic risks associated with compounding disasters. Participants will gain insights into the perspectives and challenges faced by various stakeholders during a disaster, fostering a deeper understanding and collaborative approach to disaster management.

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Learning goals & outcomes

Learning aim for participant → the change it should lead to

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Technical Requirements

The game runs on a web-based application that requires no installation—only a URL. The app is compatible with all major browsers on mobile devices, laptops, and desktops. Below are additional technical details about the simulation.

Devices

To run the simulation, both players and moderators will need suitable devices. Assuming each role is assigned to one player, every participant should have access to a smartphone, tablet, or computer (one device per role).

The moderator will need a computer and a projector (or a bigger monitor) to present the introduction and display the simulation results. Additionally, a stable Wi-Fi connection must be available for all users.

Software

- Windows: Edge 107+, Firefox 100+, Chrome 108+
- Mac: Safari 16+, Firefox 100+, Chrome 108+
- Linux: Firefox 100+, Chrome 108

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Materials

- Workshop Gameflow
- Maps and Graphs
- Evaluation survey ([link](#))

For online workshops only

- Video conferencing software, such as Zoom or Microsoft Teams, with **breakout rooms functionality**,
- Headphones and microphones for each participant and moderator,
- A webcam for each participant and moderator

For face-to-face workshops only

- A stable mobile internet router (if the local internet connection is unreliable)
- ID badges
- Printed map of Pantano and printed materials (e.g., graphs, maps.)

Setup

Remote workshops

During remote workshops, we recommend that the moderator uses two screens (if possible): one to view the participants via the video conferencing software, and the other to operate the Moderator's interface. If possible, the Player's view should also be opened on a separate screen, allowing the moderator to monitor what participants are seeing in real time.

Participants are advised to play on smartphones or other mobile devices (e.g. tablets) that meet the technical requirements listed above, and to use their computers solely for connecting with other participants via video conferencing platforms (e.g. Zoom).

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Face-to-face workshops

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The problem – Setting of High Water Pantano

The events of the past week have left many citizens of the Pantano region concerned for their safety and livelihoods. The region, home to over 600,000 people, is currently facing one of the most extreme flooding events of the century. The government is reassuring citizens that the threat is less severe than reported by the media, and that priority should be given to conducting a more comprehensive risk assessment. However, local organizations report that the window of opportunity for safe evacuation is rapidly closing. Meanwhile, some citizens are urging others to stay in the region to protect local businesses. The media is flooded with live reports as the situation appears to be slipping out of control. In response to this unprecedented crisis, the region has called upon various stakeholders to convene and decide on Pantano's future.

The Pantano High Water simulation takes place in the fictional region of Pantano, located in eastern Tellus. In recent weeks, Pantano has been grappling with two concurrent crises: prolonged droughts and an unusual surge in runoff from melting snow in the nearby mountains. In

the past few days, Tellus— Pantano's neighboring region—has suffered a catastrophic flood, devastating homes, businesses, and vital infrastructure, and leaving a path of destruction behind.

At the heart of Pantano lies its bustling urban center, Pantano City, situated downstream from the tranquil village of Phusicos. This quaint settlement plays a vital role in feeding Pantano City, serving as a key supplier of agricultural goods. Despite its proximity to the bustling metropolis, Phusicos retains its serene charm, offering a peaceful escape from the hustle and bustle of a city life while remaining easily accessible from Pantano City.

Preparation

Moderator account and logging into the simulation platform

To gain access to the moderator's account, please send an email to contact@socialsimulations.org.

The High Water Pantano simulation is hosted on engage.socialsimulations.org platform, where moderators can host their own online and face-to-face workshops.

The Moderator account is available in English. Contact us at contact@socialsimulations.org if you wish to translate the simulation into your language.

To log into the simulation:

- 1) Open engage.socialsimulations.org in your browser window. Moderators are advised to use a desktop or laptop computer. We recommend using Google Chrome or Mozilla Firefox.
- 2) Enter your login and password details into the appropriate fields. Click the "LOGIN" button.

WELCOME TO ENGAGE PLATFORM!

a

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ENTER

Creating a simulation session

To create your own session:

- 1) Select the "High Water PANTANO" template and enter a name for your session.

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2) Click "Create".

3) Use "Copy link" to copy the direct link for this specific session—this is the link you will share with the participants.

4) Click "Manage" to open and control the session from the moderator's panel.

To view both the **moderator's interface (left)** and the **participant's interface (right)**, you can open another browser or use the incognito mode in your current browser. Paste the link you copied earlier into the new window.

Creating QR codes for players and supporting moderators

Once you have created a session, you can press COPY LINK to get the link for players.

Since the links may be difficult to type on a phone's browser, we recommend creating QR codes. The application enables you to do that from the management screen of the simulation session.

Other preparations before the workshop

To ensure the workshop runs smoothly, create breakout rooms in your video conferencing platform in advance..

Check if the sound system and projector in the workshop room work properly— we suggest testing them using the introduction video.

Introducing participants to the simulation

For each part of the introduction, we provide example wording you can use. Feel free to adapt it to suit the workshop, as long as the core meaning remains intact.

Introducing the simulation concept

Goal	Text
Greetings	<i>Welcome to the Pantano High Water workshop. I'm glad you could join us today!</i>
Reason for the activity	<i>We will start our workshop in an engaging way. This simulation will give you the chance to collaborate, explore the management of systemic risk from compounding disasters, and negotiate possible solutions. Please treat it as a meaningful learning opportunity.</i> [NOTE: Adapt this section as needed based on the context of your workshop.]
General overview of the activity	<i>The activity will last approximately 2 hours. We will finish with the debriefing, which is a crucial part of the workshop.</i> - <i>No scheduled breaks are planned.</i> - <i>You will have a break after the activity.</i> - <i>Feel free to help yourself to the refreshments during the activity.</i> [NOTE: Adapt this section as needed based on the context of your workshop.]
No winners - no losers	<i>In the game we will experience today, there are no points or trophies, and the focus is not on winning. You will receive some initial guidance, but it is up to you to define them and later reflect on them.</i>

	<p>You will be able to interact with others and play your roles within a simulated society. A description of each role will give you some guidelines and impose some limitations on you, but feel free to expand it with stories you know or your own experiences.</p>
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INTRODUCING ROLES

Goal	Text
Introduction to roles	<p>As mentioned earlier, you will be playing different roles in this simulation. You will represent various residents, scientists, and decision-makers of the Pantano region.</p> <p>You will receive only basic information about your role and related constraints. You're encouraged to expand on it using your experience and imagination. Feel free to improvise— just remember to respect the limitations that come with your assigned role.</p> <p>You will determine your own goals in the simulation and consider what solutions might best suit your character. Keep this in mind as you read your role description. The debriefing session will serve as an opportunity to share your reflections with other participants.</p> <p>Let's now proceed with distributing roles.</p>
Roles	<p>Please click the link below and select a role.</p> <p>[NOTE: Add the link to the game session you have created]</p> <p><i>[For face-to-face workshops: Distribute printed role IDs to participants. You may assign specific roles to specific individuals. Hand them out as people enter the room or attach them to participant badges. For online workshops, we recommend assigning roles in advance.]</i></p>

Introduction to the simulation world

Goal	Text
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Introduction to the situation	Play the Pantano High Water simulation introduction video
Simulation timeframe	The simulation will end after a set period, because as in real life, you have limited time for important decisions. Is everything clear? Are there any questions?

PHASE 1		
Intro 3 minutes	<p>Is everybody logged in? Great! We will initiate the first phase in this world.</p> <p>[Introduction e-mails are sent automatically]</p> <p>All of you have received a "Welcome" email that contains important information.</p> <p>Please read it carefully.</p>	<p>Top bar, player's view</p>
<p>[For face-to-face workshops: divide space between groups: Scientist, Citizen (Pantano and Phusicos), Policy-maker (and/or Practitioner if there are enough participants). For online workshops –divide players into breakout rooms, with a possibility to visit other groups].</p>		

Initial instruction	If you have any questions about the content or any doubts related to the simulation, please feel free to approach me.	
Decisions 5-10 minutes	<p>[Click "Move to Voting" to move a proposal from Urgent Decisions to voting.]</p> <p>There are some difficult decisions to be made—discuss them. You will be divided into separate groups, but feel free to approach any other</p>	<p>"Decisions" -> move to voting,</p>

	<p><i>participant and discuss anything you want.</i></p> <p><i>Only the decision-makers vote in this phase; however, you can influence their decisions by visiting their table/breakout room.</i></p> <p><i>You can vote in the "Decisions" tab. Only one option will win.</i></p>	<p><i>Moderator's view</i></p>
	<p>[Publish 'Data' emails]</p> <p><i>Additional information may come your way via emails in the app— please make sure to read them carefully.</i></p>	<p><i>"Infosets" → Publish, Moderator's view</i></p>
<p>PHASE 2: CITIZENS' POLL</p>		
<p>Poll</p>	<p>[Publish Poll]</p> <p><i>Go to the 'HIDDEN' tab and click the 'MOVE TO VOTING' button</i></p>	

Press conference
3 minutes

[In online workshops — bring everyone to the plenary and close the break-out rooms]

Welcome to the press conference.

You will now learn about the voting results. According to the decision-makers' vote, option X has won.

Citizens, how do you feel about this decision? Please share your opinion in the poll that has just been published in the 'VOTING' section.

Results – Crisis
5 minutes

[Send out only one RESULTS infonet.]

RESULTS Matrix

Result 1 = Urgent Decision 1 wins (receive the majority of votes)

or

Results 2 = Urgent Decision 2 wins

or

Results 3 = Urgent Decision 3 wins

or

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	<p><i>Results 4 = Urgent Decision 4 wins</i></p> <p><i>These are the results. How do you feel about them?</i></p>	
<p>Time Travel 5-10 minutes</p>	<p><i>All is not lost! You now have the opportunity to travel 10 years back in time, before the flood had occurred.</i></p> <p><i>What decisions should have been made to minimize risks and be better prepared for the disaster? Using the information from the future, analyze knowledge gaps and vulnerabilities.</i></p> <p>[Publish REWIND emails]</p>	

Phase 3: REWIND

<p>Solution Proposition</p>	<p>[Explain the solution proposition mechanism Put "Solutions by users " ON.]</p> <p><i>You can now prepare your own proposition for the measures that can be undertaken in the region. Don't focus only on the crisis - remember you have a few years before the flood will take place. What can you do to mitigate its impact and adapt to the situation?</i></p>	<p><i>"Decisions" → "Solutions by users" - ON, Moderator's view</i></p>
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<p>Negotiations / Solutions making process</p>	<p><i>[In smaller groups, players can self-organize. In larger groups, divide players into 3-4 groups but allow them to move freely or merge.]</i></p> <p><i>You now have (5, 10 or 15) minutes to propose your ideas and encourage others to support and vote on them</i></p>	<p><i>“Decisions” → “Create Solutions” → submit, Player’s view</i></p>
<p>Voting</p>	<p><i>[Bring everyone back to the plenary.]</i></p> <p><i>You have additional (5, 10 or 15 minutes) to vote. Only 1 solution can be implemented.</i></p>	
<p>Results</p>	<p><i>The winning proposition is: (insert proposition name)</i></p> <p><i>Any comments?</i></p>	
<p>[The simulation smoothly transitions into the first part of the debriefing.]</p>		

Are you satisfied with the outcome of the voting?
 What do you think will happen once your decision is implemented?
 How successful do you think it will be?

[Outside the magic circle]

GAMEFLOW

From Phase 3, participants are free to move around the space, meet in smaller and larger groups for discussion, or to organize meetings.

The simulation may end earlier if:

1. An agreement on the decision is reached before time runs out,

2. Or participants reach a stalemate that appears unsolvable before time runs out.

The moderator's role is to monitor time and the simulation process and to announce when it ends.

DEBRIEFING

Initial questions, introduction to debriefing, and releasing tension

Now that the simulation is over, let's step out of the magic circle.

You can:

in face-to-face workshops: take off your IDs and take a seat

in online workshops: change your name back to your real name

We will now discuss what happened during the simulation.

[Time to organise]

How do you feel?

How did you feel during the simulation?

Are you satisfied with the outcome of the voting?

What do you think will happen once your decision is implemented?

How successful do you think it will be?

Further questions

Great! Now let's reflect on your actions during the simulation. Consider your role, your goals, and how the simulation unfolded.

Questions for the participants:

1. *Why did you choose your role?*
2. *What were your goals? Did you achieve them?*
3. *How did you perform?*
4. *What did you learn from your role's perspective? What was surprising for you? What challenges did you face?*

We have an opportunity to discuss this from diverse angles.

[You may use this opportunity to explain the difference between "an organiser" and "a leader"]

Questions for the participants:

- 1. How many members or supporters did you recruit or persuade to support your cause? How did this change over time?*
- 2. What tools and tactics did you use? Did you address stakeholders' problems and concerns? How did they respond?*
- 3. How did the knowledge of the crisis influence your behaviour and actions? What helped you to cope with it? What key lessons do you take away?*
- 4. Did you consider different hazards when discussing your ideas?*
- 5. What was important for you when discussing potential adaptation or mitigation options?*

Now let's consider the alternatives. How might changing your actions or approach have altered the situation.

Questions for the participants:

- 1. What would you change about your actions or approaches during the simulation?*
- 2. What would be the best path forward? What other tools and tactics could be used in the future?*

Finally, let's sum up. Please reflect on what you learned today that you'll take with you. Take a moment to think, and then we'll share.

Question for the participants:

- 1. What is your main takeaway?*
- 2. Are you going to use this experience in your work/community/group, etc.?*

Thank you for your participation. We have just finished the debriefing, which concludes our workshop. Thank you once again, and I hope you enjoyed the experience.

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